

Research on Development of Supply Chain with Lean Management in Tunisia

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Abstract: Faced with the impact of domestic and international situations, the world supply chain has begun a huge transformation, which has had an impact on Tunisian enterprises. The increasingly scarce benefits and complex and ever-changing competitive situation make it urgent for Tunisian enterprises to seek innovative ideas in management and business methods. Lean management has become an effective method to promote enterprise growth. How to use lean management to empower the efficient operation of its supply chain has become a topic that enterprises must face.

Keywords: Supply chain; Lean management; Plan; Digitization

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1.Introduction

Supply chain refers to the form of business chain formed by enterprises around production and operation activities through the link between enterprises on the chain of product suppliers and demanders, with the main goal of scientifically managing enterprise operating costs, improving product supply efficiency, achieving normal business cycle of enterprises, optimizing the interaction process between economy and social science and technology, improving industry development efficiency, and improving economic development power [1].

Developing modernization of the supply chain is an inevitable need for high-quality economic growth in Tunisia. The development of manufacturing industry is the key to national economic growth and the foundation of an industrial power [2]. In the adjustment of the world's new industrial structure, improving the intensification of the supply chain of production enterprises and utilizing modern production management methods such as data and information technology to promote the transformation of enterprises from factor driven to data driven is an important foundation for improving the high-end technology level, autonomous and controllable management level, and market competitiveness of enterprises. From the perspective of enterprise supply chain, the formation of a chain coordinated ecosystem to ensure the normal operation of enterprise production and operation activities, and the construction of a supply chain system at the enterprise level to bring a positive value chain system are the fundamental factors for enterprise growth. Figure 1 shows the effect of modernization of SCM [3].

Figure 1: Modernization effects of SCM

2. Measures to Promote Lean Management

Currently, many enterprises in Tunisia have a limited understanding of supply chain management. Some simply believe that supply chain management is procurement and production, while others believe that supply chain management is logistics. These understandings that differ from the true architecture and efficiency of the supply chain can make it difficult for enterprises to correctly identify the management elements and key points of the supply chain [4]. As a virtual concept that organically links production collaboration, the supply chain’s results in cost, quality, and schedule are related to its operational efficiency and management, whether they are positive value-added, barely maintained, or negative loss. If the type and location of products provided by enterprises on the supply chain cannot be correctly identified, it will lead to misalignment and mismatch in supply chain management, and the final business operation results will naturally not be good. Figure 2 shows the process for lean improvement [5].

Figure 2: Flow of lean improvement

2.1 Improving the Lean Management in SCM

To improve the management level of Tunisian enterprises in the supply chain, it is necessary to first analyze the problems in the current business and production activities of the enterprise, so as to implement targeted lean management in supply chain management under the guidance and guidance of the enterprise development strategy and business strategy, and ultimately improve the quality of the supply chain.

At present, Tunisian enterprises are generally at the forefront of development and business strategies, but their actual implementation is vastly different [6]. The key reason for this is the insufficient planning for undertaking strategies and strategies.

One is to carry out organizational environmental management during planning. Firstly, the identification of internal and external environmental factors. When establishing and continuously improving a management system, the enterprise should fully identify, understand, and consider various external and internal environmental factors related to the enterprise’s purpose and strategic direction, as well as factors such as laws, regulations, standards, usage needs, and guarantee conditions related to the production activities undertaken by the enterprise, which affect the enterprise’s ability to achieve the expected results of the management system [7]. Process analysis, expert evaluation, brainstorming, and other methods can be used for identification. The general internal and external environmental factors of enterprises are as follows:

1. External environmental factors: economic environment, political environment, legal and regulatory environment, technological environment, competitive environment, market environment, laws and regulations, standards, usage needs, and guarantee conditions related to production activities.
2. Internal environmental factors: core technology, patent level, values, corporate culture, personnel capabilities, organizational knowledge, and performance.

To effectively identify relevant factors, they should be divided according to the business responsibilities of different departments (as shown in Table 1). Each department should record the identification results on the “Organizational Environmental Factor Registration Form” and report it to the Planning Department for summary.

Table 1: Identification of internal and external factors

Department	External factors	Internal factors
Planning Department	Economic and political environment	Values and corporate culture
Human Resources Department	N/A	Personnel capabilities
Marketing Department	Market environment such as international and domestic market demand, competitor analysis, and other competitive environments	N/A
Technical Department	Technology innovation policies and other technological environments, as well as legal and regulatory environments; Technological development trends and other technological environments	Organizational knowledge, patent level, core technology
Quality Department	Laws, regulations, and standards related to production activities	N/A

Planning Department

Requirements and guarantee conditions
related to production activities

Organizational performance

Next is the monitoring and evaluation of internal and external environmental factors. When there are significant changes in internal and external environmental factors and before the annual management review, relevant departments should promptly revise the “Organizational Environmental Factor Registration Form” and report it to the Planning Department [8]. If necessary, a review should be conducted.

Finally, the application of internal and external environmental factors. The Planning Department summarizes the environmental factors of the enterprise and forms the “Organizational Environment Analysis Report.” Each department should identify and determine the risks and opportunities of each relevant system process based on environmental factors, develop measures to address these risks and opportunities, and fill in the response measures in the “Organizational Environmental Factor Registration Form.” The Registration Form of Organizational Environmental Factors over the years will serve as a supporting material for the preparation of medium and long-term development plans or other major strategic plans of enterprises. The Quality Department determines the scope of the management system based on the determined “Organizational Environmental Factor Registration Form” and “Organizational Environment Analysis Report,” combined with the actual situation of the enterprise’s production activities and adjusts the scope of the enterprise management system in a timely manner according to changes in environmental factors [9].

The second is that enterprises should also manage the needs and expectations of relevant parties during planning. The work process is like organizational environmental management and is divided into three steps: identification, monitoring and review, and application. However, based on the actual situation of the enterprise, relevant parties should include but not be limited to owners, customers, external suppliers, partners, employees, independent qualification recognition institutions, inspection and testing institutions, competitors, and relevant government agencies.

Thirdly, planning should include four main stages: planning, planning review, planning release and implementation, and planning update, following the PDCA iteration cycle. Specifically, it includes: determining the goals and scope, i.e. clarifying the basis information for production activities, decomposing the work structure, and forming goals; Determine human resource planning, that is, complete the planning of human resource requirements for each stage, and specify the approximate time for use and release; Determine funding planning, develop control measures, and implement plans; Determine the production activity plan, that is, refine the work objectives according to the structure, such as procurement, manufacturing, acceptance, etc.; Determine the risk management plan, clarify various risks, response measures, and implementation plans; Determining quality planning means clarifying quality assurance objectives and means, as well as control points and methods; Determine delivery and after-sales service planning; Determine the elements and goals of communication planning, namely core customers and internal and external communication [10].

2.2 Prevention and Control of Risks

Most enterprises in Tunisia are currently in the stage of neglecting management and emphasizing “supervision and handling.” The most obvious manifestation is the pursuit of “phenomenon” and the lack of in-depth work. Therefore, there is often a situation of soldiers coming to block or cover up the situation. This temporary treatment has

turned into a problem because of the risk, so there is a great possibility of failure and more resource consumption. Therefore, we should seize the opportunity before the risk occurs to prevent and control.

Risk has an uncertain impact. Uncertainty is a situation where there is a lack of understanding or knowledge about an event, its local consequences, or possibilities. Impact refers to deviation from expectations, which can be positive or negative. Usually, risk is expressed as the combination of the consequences of a certain event (including changes in circumstances) and its likelihood of occurrence, referring to various uncertain events that objectively exist in a certain environment and within a certain period and affect the achievement of goals.

To make the risk impact positive and form opportunities (i.e., conditions and events with positive impact), it is necessary to do an excellent job in the identification, assessment, and control of risk source. In terms of identification, risk source may be an internal factor that alone or jointly causes risks. For example, people or events that can bring risks can be regarded as risk source. In terms of assessment, it is a quantitative assessment of the impact and likelihood of losses caused by a risk event in various aspects before or after the event has occurred but not yet ended. Risk assessment is the quantitative assessment of the possible degree of impact or loss caused by a certain event or thing.

To ensure the correct management of risks and opportunities, enterprises need to divide their responsibilities based on departmental responsibilities. Firstly, they need to ensure that they can comprehensively identify risks and opportunities in conjunction with actual operational processes. The main challenges faced by enterprises include strategic environmental factors, market product and service requirements, knowledge management generation, solidification, confidentiality, human resource allocation, mobility, ability assessment, and financial fundraising/financing/compensation, use, recycling, etc. the main methods for identifying procurement, manufacturing, scrapping, etc. in production management, such as allocation, include checklist method, flowchart method, etc. Secondly, risk and opportunity assessment should be carried out, and all risks and opportunities inside and outside the operation planning and production activities should be analyzed and evaluated to determine their levels. The possibility and severity of the risk occurrence can be evaluated using methods such as "Risk Assessment Index Method" and "Failure Mode Impact and Criticality Analysis (FMECA)." The process experienced includes quantitative and qualitative matrix evaluation of losses, frequency of occurrence Probability and qualitative matrix evaluation, risk coefficient evaluation (correlation between degree and frequency), and determination of level. Finally, based on the actual situation, appropriate methods should be taken to address risks and opportunities, to achieve the goal of reducing or eliminating risks and effectively utilizing opportunities.

3. Lean Improvement in SCM through Digital Empowerment

The mechanized industrial revolution has improved the capabilities of equipment, but it has not helped improve the efficiency of the supply chain management process in enterprises. So with the advent of the digital industrial revolution, it has become possible to use data as the processing object to represent the situation of various links in supply chain management, make trend judgments, risk predictions, etc., effectively helping to solve the problem of insufficient personnel experience and energy caused by the increasing expansion of management elements, making it possible for enterprises to pursue the optimal solution in three aspects: product, experience, and cost simultaneously [11]. Breaking data silos, achieving on-demand data retrieval, agile self-service, and secure reliability, transforming data into assets and services, enabling smooth flow of data within the enterprise, and bringing significant benefits to the supply chain management of the enterprise. Figure 3 shows the digitalization process of SCM [12]

Figure 3: Digitalization process of SCM

3.1 Business Datafication

Supply chain management horizontally covers the entire stage from purchasing raw materials to delivering finished products, and vertically includes elements such as drawings, data, cost, progress, and quality. From stage to step, the objects of supply chain management are matrix work composed of horizontal and vertical integration. Any object has a multi-dimensional and datable attribute, and the supply chain, as a precise linkage system, The control requirements for these attributes are naturally put forward, and the data generated by their actual operation form the basis of dativization, that is, digital attributes or digital identity.

Therefore, through the continuous generation of digital identity, we can clearly use data to represent activities, processes, and entities, and represent complex content into data identities with quantitative standards. For example, we can characterize the transfer and collection of orders, the acquisition of raw materials, production and production from activities, logistics, capital flow and workflow from processes, and raw material suppliers, parts manufacturers Characterization of finished product manufacturers, distributors, and users. Through continuous iteration of digital identity, digital mapping based on iterative data can clearly show the operation of objects, trend prediction, risk probability and other important contents supporting decision-making.

The most crucial thing is that the previous work of relying on manual on-site verification and layer by layer transmission of inductive information, which cannot be done in real time, has shifted to relying on data expression and information transmission in real time. This is particularly important for improving the enterprise's rapid analysis and response ability and competing for market opportunities. The additional saved labor costs are positively correlated with the complexity and volume of the enterprise, maximizing the solution to waste, improving efficiency is also one of the driving forces for enterprises and the fundamental pursuit of lean production.

3.2 Data integration

The emergence of open globalization demands such as global markets and cross domain cooperation is an unstoppable wave that comes with the digital economy. This is a rare opportunity and huge risk for enterprises. On the one hand, enterprises have a global perspective, layout the future, and demand is everywhere. Continuously exploring new markets, enterprises can achieve great development; On the other hand, enterprises will face challenges such as continuously improving delivery speed, stabilizing quality, and saving costs, all of which require enterprises to have the ability to quickly respond to rapidly changing markets, personalized demands, flexible supply capabilities, and make accurate predictions.

As a precise linkage system, the supply chain truly possesses the characteristic of pulling the trigger and moving the whole body, which poses a necessary demand for data integration. The integration of data: First, we should describe the iterative data in the face of independent digital identity and construct individual data portraits to analyze and judge them; The second is to construct and analyze the relevance of different digital identity, and form portraits on groups, interest chains, and cooperation chains to study and judge situations or situations above individuals. By utilizing added information technologies such as big data and cloud computing, data integration can organically construct correlations between human, financial, and material factors, establishing different chains.

Within the enterprise, one approach is to predict the optimal solutions in terms of quality, cost, and progress through individual analysis. For example, typical applications include tool life prediction. By analyzing historical data on varied materials, processing parameters, tools, and machining accuracy stability, it is possible to effectively predict under what processing conditions the tool will expire, whether it will affect machining accuracy, and whether it will lead to product scrapping. In addition, pre use testing and correction can also be used, by ensuring quality, the tool life can be extended to a safe boundary, reducing the cost of early scrapping of tools, and avoiding product scrapping or equipment damage due to lifespan during processing; The second is to associate different individuals and optimize research and development production activities. For example, through digital twinning, model design data, boundary data, etc. are transmitted in real-time to the production and testing ends, achieving the function of designing while producing and verifying, achieving what you see is what you get. Once the design is completed, production verification is completed; The third is to associate diverse groups and stakeholders, identify the prominent points of cost, quality, and progress in the value chain. For example, through the value flow chart, the cumulative process of cost can be sorted out, and the most consuming link, time, and reason can be identified. Targeted solutions can be provided for single links or front and back ends. Fault mode and risk prediction can be made through factors such as product design data, process production and debugging data, and usage time, Prepare response measures and impact domain analysis in advance. Therefore, through data integration in the enterprise, it can break the traditional situation that the work interface is determined according to the specialty, business and information go their own way, reconstruct the enterprise's business ideas according to the characteristics of the supply chain management, organically connect various operations, scientific research and production activities, make the activities flow and explicit, improve the enterprise's ability to use data and information as the center, and form new competitiveness, Better and faster response to changes in demand.

Outside the enterprise, through data integration and sharing, one is to improve the efficiency of information transmission between enterprises in the supply chain. Demand and products are reflected in the form of data, reducing the process of translation and communication, enhancing mutual trust among enterprises, and greatly improving the response speed of the supply chain; The second is to make the combination of demand and supply closer, unify, and clarify size chains or interfaces due to data standards, and achieve more accurate and real-time results. From large products to small work steps, refined real-time division and cooperation have become a reality, and the flexibility and adaptability of the supply chain have been improved; Thirdly, each enterprise can make real-time judgments and responses based on the dynamics of the interest chain and cooperation chain, such as early stock preparation before price increases, VMI stock preparation, and full chain streamline, in order to reduce unnecessary production, reduce inventory, reduce costs, solve waste, and achieve lean management of the enterprise supply chain.

4. Conclusion

As can be seen from the previous text, the lean concept of demanding the elimination of all waste and improving the input-output ratio is an urgent need for high-quality development of enterprises and countries, which can make the combination of lean management and high-quality management of enterprise supply chain more powerful.

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